

THE GENESIS OF CONCEPTUAL IDEAS FOR THE FORMATION OF AN INNOVATIVE EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada, innovatsion ta'lim muhitini yuzaga keltirish, zamonaviy ta'limda kompleks o'zgarishlarni o'zida aks ettirgan innovatsion loyihalarni joriy etish, professor-o'qituvchilarning innovatsion faoliyatiga bo'lgan kasbiy kompetensiyasini zamon talabi nuqtai nazaridan o'zgartirish, zamonaviy ta'lim samaradorligi mezonini ishlab chiqish hamda innovatsion ta'lim muhitini shakllantirishning konseptual g'oyasi davlat ta'lim siyosatini zamonaviy kompleks taraqqiyot traektoriyasiga asoslanishi lozimligi ilmiy nuqtai nazardan tahlil etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Innovatsiya, ta'lim, xalqaro standart, ta'lim tizimi, barqaror innovatsion rivojlanish, zamonaviy mexanizm, taraqqiyot traektoriyasi, zamonaviy o'quv jarayon talab va tamoyili, milliy va xalqaro standart uyg'unligi, assemilyatsiya jarayoni, mobil transformatsion omillar, konsepsiya.

Аннотация: В данной статье раскрывается концептуальная идея создания инновационной образовательной среды, внедрения инновационных проектов, отражающих комплексные изменения в современном образовании, изменения профессиональной компетентности профессорско-преподавательского состава к инновационной деятельности с учетом потребностей времени, развития критерием эффективности современного образования, а также создания инновационной образовательной среды, с научной точки зрения проанализирована необходимость базирования государственной образовательной политики на траектории современного комплексного развития.

Ключевые слова: Инновации, образование, международный стандарт, образовательная система, устойчивое инновационное развитие, современный механизм, траектория развития, требования и принципы современного образовательного процесса, гармония национального и международного стандарта, процесс ассимиляции, мобильные факторы трансформации, концепция.

Abstract: In this article, the conceptual idea of creating an innovative educational environment, introducing innovative projects that reflect complex changes in modern education, changing the professional competence of professors and teachers for innovative activities in terms of the demands of the times, developing a criterion of modern educational efficiency, and creating an innovative educational environment the need to base the state education policy on the trajectory of modern complex development was analyzed from a scientific point of view.

Key words: Innovation, education, international standard, educational system, sustainable innovative development, modern mechanism, development trajectory, requirements and principle of modern educational process, harmony of national and international standard, assimilation process, mobile transformation factors, concept.

The information society is characterized by changes and developments in all spheres, the emergence of modern advanced ideas and projects and their rapid implementation in real life, the development of innovative processes in all spheres of socio-cultural life.

In today's world, innovations, reflecting the general essence of the cultural process of society, are becoming a strategic goal for the development of the innovative potential of socially organized systems and serve as a driving factor for economic sectors. This process is characterized by a scientific model that is directly based on a clear system and has a stable development trajectory. The development of all spheres of society today and the determination and forecasting of a promising strategy for tomorrow are explained by the organization and coordination of the continuity of the educational process characterized by innovative factors.

From this point of view, the creation of a competitive economy, stable social infrastructure, a seamless cultural environment, a high spiritual worldview that drives society and ensures the coherence of activities, aligns them with the interests of the state and society, the systematic formation of innovative ideas and projects, and the inculcation of patriotic elements in the personality of the individual depend on how well the education organized today and the teachers and educational environment that implement it are integrated with modern innovations.

Indeed, the prospects for social development and cultural and spiritual stability, as well as promising economic growth in the 21st century world, largely depend on the state of the education system and its ability to meet the needs of the individual and society for high-quality educational services.

From this point of view, it is appropriate to revise state educational standards today and update the main elements of the educational process based on the requirements and principles of the modern educational process. This primarily requires modern educational content, its teaching technology, increasing funds to support non-standard education and liberalizing the legal framework, as well as aligning the interconnections between all elements of the education system with innovative factors, thereby displacing the existing authoritarian approach to education from the "life" of education.

This approach, requiring a change in the educational environment and the processes taking place in it, puts on the agenda the introduction of innovative projects that reflect complex changes in education, as well as the transformation of the professional competence of professors and teachers in innovative activities from the point of view of modern requirements, as well as the development of modern criteria for the effectiveness of education.

Today, the conceptual idea of forming an innovative educational environment is characterized by basing state educational policy on a modern complex development trajectory, organizing targeted education and an education system aimed at achieving high results that meet international standards, characterized by factors of sustainable innovative development, and the creation of its modern mechanisms.

From this point of view, the introduction of innovations in educational organizations should be accompanied by the introduction of concepts such as "new", "innovation" and "innovative process" and by paying attention to the essence of these concepts and approaches.

Innovation (Russian новшество) means a new, newly created and newly applied concept, while [2] (lat. novatio) means change, renewal.

The concept of innovation is analyzed in two approaches: broad and narrow. When applied in a broad format, it is characterized by a changed algorithm of activity, reshaping existing devices based on new technologies, replacing parts, changing designs, any qualitatively new additions and changes that affect the movement and function, as well as the characteristics of the product.

In a short-form analysis, innovation is explained by a previously non-existent novelty, new theoretical knowledge, new method and principle [2].

From this point of view, innovation is the basis of a scientific and technological revolution of a revolutionary nature for every era and society, and is considered an invention that sets in motion the driver of development.

An invention is the result of research into a new device, mechanism, tool, technology, method, etc created by man.[1]

Research is characterized by obtaining previously unknown information to science and humanity, and by bringing the information learned in the process of observing nature and society into a scientific system, clarifying the trajectory of combining its theoretical foundations with practical activities.

From this point of view, despite the understanding that discoveries and inventions are the result of research and are based on the fundamental basis of innovative analysis and approach, they are carried out by individual and group inventors (researchers). Also, this process has a high probability of occurring by chance, and the fact that it is described as the result of an approach in accordance with a scientific hypothesis indicates its innovative aspect. According to our scientific analysis and approach, innovations in all areas should be classified according to the object and subject of research. The main emphasis is on the effectiveness of the result obtained, the advantage and convenience of the change, and the time and energy saving of the process, as appropriate.

It is appropriate to base our scientific reasoning on the scientific views of T.I.Budaev on innovation. According to his point of view, innovation is the replacement of an old object (phenomenon) with a new one, characterized by innovation as a process and the resulting innovation.[1]

The concept of innovation was used in scientific research carried out in the 19th century, where it mainly meant the introduction of certain elements of knowledge into another, while the concept of innovation reflected in scientific research at the beginning of the 20th century was characterized by a new field of knowledge, non-standard approaches that emerged in science and technology, and technical changes in the field of material production.

In the 21st century, the concept of innovation has a broad meaning, characterized by changes and innovations that have occurred in all fields, and is the final result of creative activity, which includes the results of scientific and theoretical research and the compatibility of categorical qualities, national and international standards, and in a certain sense reflects the process of mutual assimilation, an improved technological process of concepts combined with mobile transformation factors.

The concept of innovation, as in all fields, is gaining its place in the field of education, becoming a driver of education, expressing the criteria for the emergence of educational

technologies in a new context, and serving as a basis for training mobile specialists necessary for the state and society.

In this regard, the scientific considerations of T.N. Remizova are of great importance. In her opinion, an "innovative" approach to managing the educational and training process is of great importance, characterized by the introduction of new things into the goals, content, methods and forms of education and upbringing, and serves as the basis for bringing the organization of joint activities of participants in the educational process to a new qualitative level.[3]

In our opinion, innovation is a purposeful change that introduces new approaches and stable elements into all areas, has scientific, theoretical and practical significance, and causes a transition of a certain system and process from one state to another.

It is inappropriate to apply the concept of innovation to processes related to changes in the life of the state and society, renewal and coordination of systems, reflection of the intersection between sectors in a new format, the emergence of functional tasks, new positions and structures, and optimization, and this situation is qualified by the concept of reform. From this point of view, it is appropriate to distinguish between the concepts of "reform" and "innovation", a comparative analysis of which is presented in Table 1.

Educational reforms are an approach in the form of a social project aimed at changing the content, structure, methods and forms of education, while carrying out changes and reconstruction without destroying the foundations of the existing social structure.

Reforms in the field of higher education create a healthy competitive environment in the market of educational services, introduce advanced standards of higher education, raise the content of higher education to a qualitatively new level, and create a system for training highly qualified personnel.

Also, educational reform involves the introduction of non-fundamental and normative changes and changes into this process, without affecting the functional foundations of the existing education system in society.

Innovation in the field of education is a pedagogical innovation aimed at developing educational methods, enriching and improving the quality of educational content, organizing the educational process, improving learning technologies and assessing them. Innovations in education are characterized by relevant and systematically self-organizing innovations that are promising for the evolution of education and have a positive impact on the development of all forms and methods of education. Also, innovations in education arise in the specific context of teaching, in improving the implementation of standard practices and introducing new practices, and are manifested in achieving quality learning outcomes, identifying problems arising in the educational process, and developing new methods for solving these problems.

Table 1

Reform	Innovation
Changing the dates of the study process in the educational system	Introducing new methodologies into the education system and learning process
Changing the equipment of educational institutions	Introduction of modern pedagogical technology to the educational process
Changing the duration of education	Applying elements of artificial intelligence

	to the educational process
Division of the educational process into bachelor's and master's degrees	Realization of specialist training system based on individual education technology in practice

In conclusion, the difference between reform and innovation is that while reform is carried out by government bodies on the basis of certain decisions, laws, and orders, innovation is developed and implemented by researchers, academics, and organizations operating in the science and technology system.

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